

FINITE DEFORMATION OF FABRIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

An nonlinear constitutive relation, based on the concept of finite elasticity and a Lagrangian strain energy density, for a unit cell of plain weave fabric flexible composite under finite deformation, is presented. The warp and filling yarns in a unit cell are assumed in the shape of a sinusoidal wave. The actual fabric geometry, and the properties of fiber and matrix are used in the theoretical predictions. Reasonable correlations have been found between theory and experiments.

KEY WORDS: Composite; Fabric; Constitutive Relation; Finite Deformation; Modeling.

1. INTRODUCTION

Elastomeric (flexible) composites have had broad applications in synthetic biological materials, various kinds of membrane structures, and pneumatic tires. The fabric flexible composites used in this study are of particular interest since their large usable deformation can be easily reached while their superior strength retained in a highly controlled manner.

Flexible composites behave significantly different from conventional rigid polymer composites in the following ways:

1. Flexible composites are highly anisotropic (i.e. longitudinal elastic modulus/transverse elastic modulus $\gg 1$). Figure 1 compares the normalized effective Young's modulus (E_{xx}/E_{22}) vs. fiber orientation for two types of unidirectional composites. The upper curve obtained from Kevlar-49/silicone elastomer shows that the stiffness of the elastomeric composite lamina is very sensitive to the fiber orientation. At a 5° off-axis fiber orientation, for example, a 1° change in fiber angle causes the effective stiffness to change by 53%. The lower curve obtained from Kevlar-49/epoxy shows less than 7% change at the same off-axis angle.

2. Flexible composites show low shear modulus and hence large shear distortion, which allows the fibers to change their orientations under load.

3. Flexible composites have much larger elastic deformation range than that of conventional rigid polymer composites. Thus, the geometric changes of the configuration (i.e. area, direction, etc.) need to be taken into consideration.

4. The nonlinear elastic behavior with stretching-shear coupling, due to material and geometrical effects, is pronounced in flexible composites under finite deformation.

Composite lamination theory has been widely used in the study of fabric composites with a rigid matrix [1, 2]. However, the flexible composite often involves nonlinear finite deformations [3]. In order to fully realize the ability of flexible composites under large deformation, the conventional linear elastic theory based on the infinitesimal strain assumption for rigid matrix composites is no longer applicable.

To analyze the rubber coated fabrics under finite deformation, truss models are often used [4-6]. In these models, usually, the curved yarns and the matrix are replaced by equivalent straight bars. Unlike pure fabric, if the fabric is embedded in a matrix, the non-affine displacement is restricted [7]. With a soft matrix, the fabric composite properties become much harder than pure fabric and matrix. Also, as shown Fig.1, the properties of flexible composite are very sensitive to the fiber orientation when the initial angle is small. Thus, it is very critical to determine the equivalent truss geometry and the equivalent properties of the matrix in the truss analysis. The theoretical determination is difficult.

Adkins and Rivlin [8] first presented an exact theory to study the behavior of unidirectional cord reinforced rubber sheet. The concept of finite elasticity, the assumptions of volume incompressibility and fiber inextensibility are basic to the analysis. Recently, Luo, Chou and Rivlin [9-12] conducted a series of researches on the constitutive equations of flexible composite laminae, laminates, and wavy fiber reinforced composites under nonlinear finite deformation. They found an agreement between the theories and experiments.

In this work, the plain weave Kevlar fabric (Fig. 2) reinforced with silicon rubber is chosen as a material system. The theoretical prediction is based on the analysis of a wavy flexible composite under nonlinear finite deformation. A unit cell model containing two pair of perpendicular sinusoidally shaped yarns is shown in Fig. 3(b). The unit cell is further regarded as an assemblage of a finite number of unidirectional flexible fiber composites with different fiber orientations and volume fractions. By applying the Luo and Chou wavy model, the elastic behavior of fabric flexible composite under unidirectional tension is predicted by using the information of the actual fabric geometry, and the properties of fiber and matrix. Reasonable correlations have been found between the theory and experiments.

2. ANALYSIS

2.1 Unit cell of Plain Weave Fabric Reinforced Composite Due to the complexity of the reinforcement geometry, stress inhomogeneity exists throughout the fabric composite structure. In order to understand the overall behavior of the fabric composite structure, our emphasis shall focus on a unit cell which is the smallest representative element with a similar fabric architecture [2]. If such a unit cell can be identified and the effective constitutive relation of such element can be predicted, similar to the conventional finite element method, the force-deformation relation of the whole composite structure can be determined.

A typical unit cell of a plain weave fabric composite (Fig.3(b)) contains two curved warp yarns and two curved filling yarns in a matrix. In general, due to the processing, warp yarns have larger crimp than the filling yarns. By reviewing the photographs of the cross-section of fabric composites (Fig 3(a)), it is reasonably to assume that the yarns are in the shape of sinusoidal wave. Let the coordinates x and y represent the warp and filling yarn directions, respectively. The spatial position of a fiber with sinusoidal waviness in the x - z coordinate system (Fig.4(a)) is specified as

$$z = a_x \sin \frac{2\pi x}{L_x} \quad (2.1)$$

where a_x and L_x represent the amplitude and wavelength of the curved yarn. By using the normalized parameters,

$$\alpha = \frac{a_x}{L_x}, \quad \xi = \frac{x}{L_x}, \quad Z = \frac{z}{L_x}, \quad S = \frac{s}{L_x} \quad (2.2)$$

where s is the total length of a yarn between $x = 0$ and L_x . The geometry of a warp yarn is then defined as,

$$Z = \alpha \sin 2\pi\xi, \quad (2.3)$$

The fiber orientation angle (θ) at ξ is obtained by

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{dz}{dx} \right) = \tan^{-1} (2\pi\alpha \cos 2\pi\xi) \quad (2.4)$$

The normalized length of a yarn, between $\xi = 0$ and 1, is given as [13]:

$$S = 1 + 2\left[\frac{k^2}{8}\right] + 13\left[\frac{k^2}{8}\right]^2 + 90\left[\frac{k^2}{8}\right]^3 + 644\left[\frac{k^2}{8}\right]^4 + 4708.5\left[\frac{k^2}{8}\right]^5 + \dots \quad (2.5)$$

where

$$k^2 = \frac{(2\pi\alpha)^2}{1+(2\pi\alpha)^2}$$

Notice that, from the equations above, the yarn geometry can be identified by using a single parameter α which is the ratio of wave amplitude over wavelength and can be measured directly from actual fabrics. The second warp yarn in the unit cell is symmetric to the first yarn about the mid-plane, and has 180° difference in fiber orientation angle. The geometries of the filling yarn can be determined by the similar treatment of the warp yarn, with the change of coordinate from x to y .

2.2 Elastic Properties of a Sub-Element Under loading, the inhomogeneous deformation exists throughout the unit cell due to the inhomogeneity distribution of the fibers. To study the details of the stress-strain condition, a unit cell can be further regarded as an assemblage of a finite number of unidirectional fiber composites. Fig. 4(a) illustrates a unit cell that has been divided into n sub-elements along the warp (ξ) axis. It is clear that each sub-element has different fiber orientations and volume fractions. Consequently, each sub-element has different elastic properties which should be predicted by using the fabric geometric parameters and the properties of its constituents (i.e., fiber and matrix).

Usually, the angle between the warp yarn and the ξ axis is small. Referring to Eq.(2.4), the off-axis angle of sub-element i , between ξ and $\xi+\Delta\xi$, is

$$\beta_i = \tan^{-1} (2\pi\alpha \cos 2\pi(\xi+\Delta\xi/2)) \quad (2.6)$$

The sub-element containing the minimum warp fiber volume fraction, V_{wf}^{\min} , occurs at $\beta = 0$ (or $\xi = \pi/4, 3\pi/4$) and $\Delta\xi \rightarrow 0$.

$$V_{wf}^{\min} = \frac{2A_{wf}}{L_y} \quad (2.7)$$

where A_{wf} is the cross section area of fibers in a warp yarn. The volume fraction of warp fiber of an arbitrary sub-element i is given as

$$V_{wf}^i = \frac{1}{\cos\beta_i} V_{wf}^{\min} \quad (2.8)$$

The average warp fiber volume fraction of the fabric composite, V_{wf}^{average} , is the summation of all the sub-elements' fiber volume fraction,

$$V_{wf}^{\text{average}} = V_{wf}^{\min} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\cos\beta_i} \quad (2.9)$$

Thus, when either the average warp fiber volume fraction or the fiber cross section area of a warp yarn is measured, the warp fiber volume fraction of any sub-element, V_{wf}^i , can be determined. Fig.7 and 8 illustrate both fiber orientation angle and volume fraction as functions of ξ .

All the filling yarns are perpendicular to the ξ axis. The angle between the filling yarns and the Z axis usually is large, the elastic properties are insensitive to the angle change as shown in Fig.1. The calculation also shows that the transverse properties (E_{33} and G_{23}) of flexible composites are not sensitive to the change of the fiber volume fraction. When the load is applied in the ξ direction, the filling yarn may be assumed uniformly distributed in the matrix and behaves as a transversely isotropic material. The idealized unit cell ξ - Z cross section is shown in Fig. 4(b). The shaded area shows composite with filling fiber, and has the fiber volume fraction,

$$V_{ff} = \frac{V_{ff}^{\text{average}}}{1 - V_{wf}^{\text{average}}} \quad (2.10)$$

To determine the elastic properties, the sub-element is considered as an off-axis unidirectional lamina. The shaded part of Fig. 4(b) is equivalent to the matrix material with the equivalent Young's modulus, shear modulus, and Poisson's ratio,

$$E_m^* = E_{33}, \quad G_m^* = G_{23}, \quad \nu_m^* = E_m^*/2G_m^* - 1 \quad (2.11)$$

where E_{33} and G_{23} are predicted from the composite micro-mechanics equations with the given fiber and matrix properties. The fiber volume fraction is V_{ff} (Eq.(2.9)). (In this work, Halpin-Tsai equation [14] is used). Then, the elastic properties of the sub-element in respect to the material principal coordinate x_1 - x_2 (Fig.5) are determined by applying Halpin-Tsai equation again. The fiber volume fraction is V_{wf}^i (Eq.(2.8)), and the matrix properties are obtained from Eq.(2.11).

2.3 Constitutive Relation of Fabric Flexible Composite Under Unidirectional Tension

Because of the low shear modulus of the matrix and the highly anisotropic nature ($E_1 \gg E_2$) of the flexible composites, the fiber reorientation may be quite large under loading. The effective elastic properties of the composite are very sensitive to the fibre orientation. The geometric nonlinearity of the flexible composite is mainly caused by the reorientation of fibres. The material nonlinearity is also pronounced in elastomeric composites under large deformation.

To treat the anisotropic nonlinear finite deformation problem, the Luo & Chou wavy flexible composite model [11] is applied. This model is based upon the Lagrangian description and a Lagrangian strain-energy density referring to the initial principal material coordinates.

Under the uniaxial tensile force F_1 in the X_1 direction, the following plane stress condition of the flexible composite is assumed:

$$\Pi_{11} = F_1/A_0, \quad \Pi_{22} = 0, \quad \Pi_{21} = 0 \quad (2.12)$$

where Π_{ij} is the Lagrangian stress (also known as Piola-Kirchoff stress) defined as force per unit initial area. A_0 is the initial cross-sectional area ($=h \cdot L_y$) perpendicular to the ξ axis.

Notice that, due to large deformation, the Lagrangian stress is not a symmetric stress, i.e., $\Pi_{21} \neq \Pi_{12}$.

Fig.6 shows the deformation of a typical sub-element PQQ'P'. pqq'p' represents the configuration in the deformed state. This deformation is specified as "simple shear superposed on simple extension" and the constitutive relations are given in the following,

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_{11} &= \lambda_1 [\cos^2\beta W_{11} + \sin^2\beta W_{22} - \cos\beta \sin\beta W_{12}] \\ \Pi_{22} &= [\sin^2\beta W_{11} + \cos^2\beta W_{22} + \cos\beta \sin\beta W_{12}] \\ \Pi_{21} &= [\cos\beta \sin\beta W_{11} - \cos\beta \sin\beta W_{22} + \frac{1}{2}(\cos^2\beta - \sin^2\beta)W_{12}] \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

Here, W is the strain energy density in terms of the Lagrangian strains, \bar{E}_{ij} . In this study, only the linear material properties are considered (i.e., only the linear terms are remained in W). The following can be obtained:

$$\begin{aligned}
W_{11} &= \frac{\partial W}{\partial \bar{E}_{11}} = Q_{11} \bar{E}_{11} + Q_{12} \bar{E}_{22} \\
W_{22} &= \frac{\partial W}{\partial \bar{E}_{22}} = Q_{22} \bar{E}_{22} + Q_{12} \bar{E}_{11} \\
W_{12} &= \frac{\partial W}{\partial \bar{E}_{12}} = 4Q_{66} \bar{E}_{12}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.14}$$

Where Q_{ij} is the reduced elastic stiffness constants [14], and

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{E}_{11} &= \frac{1}{4}[(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 - 2 + \lambda_1^2 K^2) + (\lambda_1^2 - \lambda_2^2 - \lambda_1^2 K^2) \cos 2\beta + 2K\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \sin 2\beta] \\
\bar{E}_{22} &= \frac{1}{4}[(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 - 2 + \lambda_1^2 K^2) + (\lambda_1^2 - \lambda_2^2 - \lambda_1^2 K^2) \cos 2\beta - 2K\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \sin 2\beta] \\
\bar{E}_{12} &= \frac{1}{4}[(\lambda_2^2 - \lambda_1^2 - \lambda_1^2 K^2) \sin 2\beta + 2K\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \cos 2\beta].
\end{aligned} \tag{2.15}$$

Thus, in Eq.(2.13), there are three equations and three unknowns, λ_1 , λ_2 , and K . Where λ_1 and λ_2 are the principal extension ratio in ξ and z , K is the amount of shear as defined in Fig.4(b). With the given stress condition Eq.(2.12) these unknown can be solved from Eqs. (2.13). The average extension ratio of the unit cell in the ξ direction is the summation of all the sub-elements' extension ratio $\lambda_1^{(i)}$,

$$\lambda_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_1^{(i)} \tag{2.16}$$

Notice that the above analysis only considers the load applied in the warp direction. Similar treatment can be applied to study the filling direction response with the index change from x to y .

3. EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Specimens The specimens of Kevlar fabric/silicone elastomer composite were fabricated by the authors. The matrix material is SYLGARD 184 silicone elastomer matrix, supplied by Dow Corning Co. Two types of Kevlar fabrics have been used. The measured geometries are listed as the following:

	a_x/L_x	a_y/L_y	weight per area	corss-section area	$V_{wf}^{average}$	$V_{ff}^{average}$
Type 1	0.0225	0.0225	0.00603 g/cm ²	0.01567 mm ²	0.0174	0.0174
Type 2	0.081	0.039	0.0333 g/cm ²	0.1139 mm ²	0.0583	0.0562

The ratio $\alpha = a/L$ is a very important parameter to describe the fabric geometry. Two measurement methods have been used: (1) The cross section of the composite specimens have been examined under a microscope, and microscopy photographs are taken. The ratio α is measured directly from these photographs. (2) The length of the fabric was measured first. Then, the yarns were detached from the fabric and the straight yarn lengths were measured. The ratio α was determined by Eq. (2.5). At least 10 samples had been taken for each measurement. The average fiber volume fraction were obtained by $(2 A_f s)/(\text{volume of a unit cell})$, where A_f was the fiber cross section area of a yarn and s was determined from Eq.(2.5). The elastic properties of the fiber and matrix are given as the following:

	Young's modulus	Shear modulus	Poisson's ratio	Density
Fiber	110 Gpa	43.036Mpa	0.278	1.44g/cm ³
Matrix	4.826Mpa	1.65Mpa	0.46	1.05 g/cm ³

To make the fabric flexible composite, a sheet of fabric with pre-coating (SYLGARD prime cost liquid) and end tabs was placed on a plate which was covered with a Teflon thin film. A frame, with the same thickness as that of the composite, was placed around the fabric to prevent the resin from flowing out. The assembly then was placed in a vacuum chamber connected to a vacuum pump. The mixed resin (air bubble removed) was poured in through two pipes on the top of the container. During pouring, the vacuum pump should work continuously to eliminate the air in the composites. The composites were cured at room temperature for 48 hours first, and then put in an oven with a temperature of 45°C for another 48 hours.

3.2 Testing Tensile tests were performed on an Instron Tester with cross-head speed 2.5mm/min. The specimen dimensions in test section were 25 mm X 178 mm. The thickness for fabric type 1 is 0.0418mm, and for type 2 is 0.231 mm. To measure the deformation, a photographic method was used. At each pre-determined stress level, a photograph was taken to record the deformed configuration of the grid pre-marked on the specimen. The initial grid was 20 mm x 50 mm. Measurements of the locations of the marks on the specimen determine the displacements.

4. COMPARISONS

To verify the constitutive equations developed in the previous sections, the theoretical predictions were compared to the experimental results. The material systems examined were: (1) Kevlar fabric/silicone elastomer with the ratio $\alpha = a/L = 0.0225$ for both warp and filling yarns; (2) Kevlar fabric/silicone elastomer with the ratio $\alpha = 0.081$ for warp yarn, and $\alpha = 0.039$ for filling yarns. The detail specimen specification, fiber and matrix properties, and testing methods have been described in Sec. 3. The formulae used in the prediction can be found in Sec. 2.2 and 2.3. The inelastic behavior generally occurs in large deformation problems. Our experiments indicate that the inelastic strain is small compared with the total strain of the specimens. Thus, for simplification, elastic behavior is assumed for the material systems used in this work.

Fig. 9 (a) and (b) shows the comparison between analytical predictions and experimental results for the plain weave Kevlar fabric/elastomer composite under simple tension. Here, the Lagrangian stress Π_1 (i.e., load/original cross-sectional area) and $\lambda_1 - 1$ (i.e., increment in length/original length) were used. The solid line indicates the theoretical prediction from the present theory; the dots indicate experimental results.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND REMARKS

The nonlinear constitutive relation for a unit cell of plain weave fabric flexible composite under finite deformation has been presented. The warp and filling yarns in a unit cell are assumed in the shape of a sinusoidal wave. The unit cell is further regarded as an assemblage of a finite number of unidirectional flexible composites with different fiber orientations and volume fractions. The elastic behavior of the sub-elements are predicted by using the constitutive equation developed for flexible composites containing sinusoidally shaped fibers; the analysis is based on the concept of finite elasticity and a Lagrangian strain energy density. The actual fabric geometry, and the properties of fiber and matrix are used in the theoretical predictions. Reasonable correlations have been found between theory and experiments for a plain weave Kevlar fabric/elastomer composite under simple tension.

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Fig 1. Variation of effective modulus with fiber orientation

Fig 2 Plain weave fabric composite structure

(a)

(b)

Fig 3 (a) Microphotograph of a cross section of plain weave fabric composites
(b) A unit cell model of plain weave fabric composites

Fig 4 (a) Cross section of a unit cell
(b) Cross section of an Idealized unit cell

Fig 5 An idealized sub-element

Fig 6 Deformation of a sub-element

Fig 7 Fiber orientation angle vs. ξ

Fig 8 Fiber volume Fraction vs. ξ

Fig. 9 Stress-strain relations of Kevlar fabric/silicone elastomer composite for (a) fabric type 1, (b) fabric type 2. Solid lines indicate theoretical predictions, dots indicate experimental results.